

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Indexing

CERTIFICATE

OF PUBLICATION

TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN

ISSN (E): 2992-9148
ResearchBib Impact
Factor: 9.576 / 2024

Buzrukov To'liqin Omonovich

FOR PUBLICATION OF PAPER ENTITLED
THEME: BIOLOGICAL FLUID VISCOSITY: PHYSIOLOGICAL BASIS,
DETERMINANTS AND CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

19.04.2026

DATE

ESHKARAEV S.CH
EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN

Buzrukov To'iqin Omonovich

WAS AWARDED A

DIPLOM

ISSN (E): 2992-9148

ResearchBib Impact

Factor: 9.576 / 2024

FOR AN ARTICLE ON THE SUBJECT OF THEME:

**BIOLOGICAL FLUID VISCOSITY: PHYSIOLOGICAL BASIS, DETERMINANTS AND
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE**

19.04.2026

DATE

**ESHKARAEV S.CH
EDITOR-IN-CHIEF**

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

ISSN (E): 2992-9148
ResearchBib Impact
Factor: 9.576 / 2024

TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN

Mamasoatova Sevinch Yaxhiboyevna

FOR PUBLICATION OF PAPER ENTITLED
THEME: BIOLOGICAL FLUID VISCOSITY: PHYSIOLOGICAL BASIS,
DETERMINANTS AND CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

19.04.2026

DATE

ESHKARAEV S.CH
EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN

Mamasoatova Sevinch Yaxhiboyevna

WAS AWARDED A

DIPLOM

ISSN (E): 2992-9148

ResearchBib Impact

Factor: 9.576 / 2024

FOR AN ARTICLE ON THE SUBJECT OF THEME:

BIOLOGICAL FLUID VISCOSITY: PHYSIOLOGICAL BASIS, DETERMINANTS AND
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

19.04.2026

DATE

ESHKARAEV S.CH
EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

ResearchBib Impact Factor: 9.576 / 2024

MUALLIFLIK GUVOHNOMASI

ISSN (E): 2992-9148

Ushbu guvohnoma «Technical Science Research in Uzbekistan» ilmiy jurnalining 2026-yil 04-sonida chop etilgan quyidagi ilmiy maqolaga mualliflik qilgani uchun berildi:

MAVZU: BIOLOGICAL FLUID VISCOSITY: PHYSIOLOGICAL BASIS, DETERMINANTS AND CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Maqola qabul qilingan sana: 19.04.2026

Maqola mualliflari: Buzrukov To'liq Omonovich, Mamasoatova Sevinch Yaxhiboyevna

Technical Science Research in Uzbekistan

